

Biosynthesis and analytics of specialized pro-resolving mediators: facts and faults

Nils Helge Schebb^{1*}, Hartmut Kühn², Nadja Kampschulte¹, Nicolas Flamand³, Marc Peters-Golden⁴, Per-Johan Jakobsson⁵, Hans-Erik Claesson⁶, Karsten H. Weylandt^{7,8}, Nadine Rohwer^{7,8,9}, Meike J. Saul¹⁰, Eugen Proschak^{11,12}, Bernhard Brüne¹³, Ulrike Garscha¹⁴, Thorsten J. Maier¹⁵, Paola Patrignani¹⁶, Miguel A. Gijón¹⁷, Francisco J. Schopfer¹⁸, Stacy L. Gelhaus¹⁹, Michael H. Gelb²⁰, Robert C. Murphy²¹, Carsten Skarke²², Alan R. Brash²³, Bruce A. Freeman¹⁸, Ian A. Blair^{24,25}, Derek W. Gilroy²⁶, Gerd Geisslinger^{27,12}, Julien Hanson²⁸, Kim Ekroos²⁹, Garret A. FitzGerald²², Astrid S. Kahnt¹¹, Valerie B. O'Donnell^{30*}, Mohamad Wessam Alnouri³¹, Stefan Offermanns^{31,32*}, Dieter Steinhilber^{11,12*}

¹Food Chemistry, Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences, University of Wuppertal, Gausstr. 20, 42119 Wuppertal, Germany

²Department of Biochemistry, Charité-Universitätsmedizin Berlin, Corporate Member of Freie Universität Berlin and Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Charitéplatz 1, 10117 Berlin, Germany.

³Centre de recherche de l'Institut universitaire de cardiologie et de pneumologie de Québec, Département de médecine, Faculté de médecine, Université Laval, Québec City, QC G1V 4G5, Canada

⁴Division of Pulmonary and Critical Care Medicine, Department of Internal Medicine, University of Michigan Medical School, Ann Arbor, MI USA

⁵Division of Rheumatology, Department of Medicine Solna, Karolinska Institutet & Karolinska University Hospital, Center for Molecular Medicine, SE-17176 Stockholm

⁶Department of Medicine, Karolinska University Hospital Solna, SE-17176 Stockholm, Sweden

⁷Division of Gastroenterology & Endocrinology and Nutrition Skills Lab, University Hospital Ruppiner-Brandenburg, Brandenburg Medical School, 16816 Neuruppin, Germany

⁸Faculty of Health Sciences, Joint Faculty of the Brandenburg University of Technology, Brandenburg Medical School and University of Potsdam, 14469 Potsdam, Germany

⁹Department of Molecular Toxicology, German Institute of Human Nutrition Potsdam-Rehbruecke, 14558 Nuthetal, Germany

¹⁰Department of Oncology, Hematology and Bone Marrow Transplantation with Section Pneumology, University Medical Center Hamburg-Eppendorf, 20246 Hamburg, Germany

¹¹Institute of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Goethe University Frankfurt, Max-von-Laue-Str. 9, 60438 Frankfurt, Germany

¹²Fraunhofer Institute for Translational Medicine and Pharmacology, ITMP and Fraunhofer Cluster of Excellence for Immune mediated diseases, CIMD, 60590 Frankfurt am Main, Germany

¹³Institute of Biochemistry I, Faculty of Medicine, Goethe University Frankfurt, Theodor-Stern-Kai 7, 60590 Frankfurt, Germany

¹⁴Department of Pharmaceutical/Medicinal Chemistry, Institute of Pharmacy, Greifswald University, Friedrich-Ludwig-Jahn-Str. 17, 17489 Greifswald, Germany

¹⁵Department of Immunology, Paul-Ehrlich-Institute (Federal Institute for Vaccines and Biomedicines), 63225 Langen, Germany

¹⁶Department of Neuroscience, Imaging and Clinical Sciences, and Center for Advanced Studies and Technology (CAST), "G. d'Annunzio" University, 66100 Chieti, Italy

¹⁷Cayman Chemical Company, Ann Arbor, Michigan, USA

¹⁸Department of Pharmacology and Chemical Biology, University of Pittsburgh, School of Medicine, Pittsburgh, PA 15261, USA

¹⁹Department of Pharmacology and Chemical Biology, Health Sciences Mass Spectrometry Core, University of Pittsburgh, Pittsburgh, PA 15261, USA

²⁰Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry, University of Washington, Seattle, WA 98195, USA

²¹Department of Pharmacology, University of Colorado-Denver, Aurora, CO 80045, USA

²²Institute for Translational Medicine and Therapeutics, Perelman School of Medicine, University of Pennsylvania, Philadelphia, Pennsylvania 19104, USA

²³Department of Pharmacology, Vanderbilt University, Nashville, TN 37232, USA

²⁴Penn/CHOP Friedreich Ataxia Center of Excellence, Perelman School of Medicine, University of Pennsylvania, Philadelphia, PA 19104, USA

²⁵Department of Systems Pharmacology and Translational Therapeutics, Perelman School of Medicine, University of Pennsylvania, Philadelphia, PA 19104, USA

²⁶Dept. of Ageing, Rheumatology and Regenerative Medicine, University College London, London WC1E 6JF, UK

²⁷Institute of Clinical Pharmacology, Faculty of Medicine, Goethe-University Frankfurt, Theodor-Stern-Kai 7, 60590 Frankfurt am Main, Germany

²⁸Laboratory of Molecular Pharmacology, GIGA Research Institute & CIRM, University of Liège, Liège, Belgium

²⁹Lipidomics Consulting Ltd., Irisviksvägen 31D, 02230 Esbo, Finland

³⁰Systems Immunity Research Institute, School of Medicine, Cardiff University, Cardiff CF14 4XN, UK

³¹Max Planck Institute for Heart and Lung Research, Department of Pharmacology, 61231 Bad Nauheim, Germany

³²Center for Molecular Medicine, Goethe University Frankfurt, 60590 Frankfurt, Germany

****Corresponding Author Information; these authors share senior authorship:**

Nils Helge Schebb, nils@schebb-web.de

Valerie O'Donnell, O-DonnellVB@cardiff.ac.uk

Stefan Offermanns, stefan.offermanns@mpi-bn.mpg.de

Dieter Steinhilber, steinhilber@em.uni-frankfurt.de

Abstract

Specialized pro-resolving mediators (SPMs) have been suggested to act as key factors that mediate the resolution of inflammation. With the availability of synthetic standards, pharmacological studies have garnered support for the hypothesis. However, assessment of the catalytic properties of lipoxygenases as well as investigations of the signalling of the proposed SPM receptors raise serious doubt that SPMs are endogenous mediators of the resolution of inflammation. In line with this, careful evaluation of published data on SPM detection revealed a lack of evidence for many reported SPMs in biological samples due to analytical LC-MS/MS methods that do not meet the quality standards of the scientific community, or they rely on ELISAs that lack selectivity and are not suited for the establishment of the presence of SPMs in complex biological samples. Furthermore, artefacts due to autoxidation of PUFAs can be misinterpreted as SPM formation. In this review, we critically assess the published reports on the biosynthesis and the analysis of SPMs and summarize the current status in the field.

Keywords: lipoxygenase, leukotriene, resolving, lipoxin, SPM receptor, resolution

Introduction

Oxylipins are formed by lipoxygenase (LOX), cyclooxygenase and cytochrome P450 enzymes from polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA), predominantly linoleic (LA), arachidonic (AA), eicosapentaenoic (EPA) and docosahexaenoic (DHA) acids. The prostaglandins and leukotrienes are mediators involved in the regulation of various physiological functions, including pro-inflammatory roles that are countered in therapeutics by NSAIDs or receptor antagonists. With contrasting activities, a subset of oxylipins, termed specialized pro-resolving lipid mediators (SPMs) are proposed to support the resolution of inflammation (1-4). SPMs such as lipoxins (LX), resolvins (Rv), maresins (MaR) and protectins (PD) are proposed to be formed by LOX from AA, EPA or DHA (Figure 1). However, a first report which failed to detect SPMs in human plasma and urine even after supplementation of patients with EPA and DHA was published in 2015 (5). Data consistent with the null hypothesis were subsequently published from other laboratories (reviewed in (6)). Apart from patient data, there is accumulating evidence from biochemical assays and cell assays that human leukocytes lack the biosynthetic capacities to produce relevant levels of SPMs. Furthermore, analytical methods to detect SPMs in biological samples have been challenged (6-8). This review provides an update of the SPM biosynthesis and analytics highlighting the ongoing problems with SPM detection in biological samples by liquid chromatography and tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) methods and ELISAs. Overall, it can be concluded that evidence for enzymatic formation of most SPMs from endogenous PUFA substrates in cells and tissues is missing and that autoxidation can represent a significant artefactual source of the oxylipins.

Analytical detection of SPMs

(i) Analytical detection of SPMs using LC-MS/MS.

The detection and quantification of SPMs is generally carried out using liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS). However, for many years up to around 2020, only a few analytical laboratories routinely reported their detection in biological samples using LC-MS/MS (9-12). Other laboratories monitored for the presence of SPMs using oxylipin platforms, but SPMs were not conclusively found (5, 13, 14). Indeed, a study which showed primary data 10 years ago concluded that even with fish oil supplementation, convincing signals for SPM were not detected in plasma or urine of healthy subjects (5). During that time, negative data on the absence of SPMs in biological samples was not routinely published, making evaluation of the issue difficult. Subsequently, in 2023, it was noted that some laboratories routinely detecting SPMs using LC-MS/MS were interpreting their data differently from the community norm, by (i) annotating poor quality MS/MS spectra for the presence of “diagnostic ions”, (ii) not requiring the presence of a chromatographic peak, or (iii) applying limit of detection (LOD) or limit of quantitation (LOQ) criteria that were based on a single integrated area (cps) for all analytes (7, 8, 15). Adding to the confusion, it was also noted that around 80 publications contained figures of what were labelled in publications as chromatographic traces of tissue SPMs, but then were clarified by the authors to represent “illustrations” or “schematics”, being shown in place of actual data (16, 17). Furthermore, as reported in an editorial note in 2025, around 15 of these included the same illustration, labelled as different tissues across the studies (18). A small number have been corrected, by clarifying that illustrated peaks were not real data (19-22). It has never been explained why the real data was not shown, as had been claimed in figure legends (19-22). Because for the majority of these studies, the raw data are not provided, the presence of SPMs cannot be established. For the few that included chromatograms in corrections/addendums, the data quality is mixed. For example in Mai et al., many peaks are of extremely poor quality that do not establish the presence of SPMs (23), while the correction to Werz et al. adequately shows that RvD2 and RvD5 or its isomers are detected in human macrophage lipid extracts (24).

Reviewing other recent studies, Werz and colleagues claimed to detect RvD5, RvE4, PD1, PDX, Mar1 and LXA₄ or its isomers in primary human macrophages under various conditions (25-27). However, a recent chiral analysis showed that PD1 is not formed by human macrophages raising doubts about some of the initial findings (28, 29). In another recent paper, Mar2, RvD2 and RvD1 were reportedly formed by human macrophages (30). However, these claims cannot be verified since chromatograms were not shown and raw data are not currently available online. For a small number of recent studies from Dalli et al., raw LC-MS/MS data have been deposited on BioStudies (31-36). However, the reported SPMs in these are questionable with the chromatograms failing to show discernable peaks at expected retention times. Examples of this issue are shown for five of these studies (Figures 3,4 in (37)). Raw LC-MS/MS chromatograms from a study investigating MCTR compounds lack any visible peaks for MCTR1, MCTR2 and MCTR3 in macrophages, while data from another study lacks peaks for 6 of the 7 SPMs claimed to be detected in mouse plasma (Figure 3 in (37)) (31, 35, 38). Data in a third paper lack chromatographic peaks for many oxylipins including SPMs from cultured cells (Figure 3 in (37)) (39). Readers are referred to PubPeer threads, which give

further detail on these studies (40-42). Two additional publications from the Dalli group were assessed during drafting of this review. In one, a frameshift variant in LRG6 (an orphan receptor claimed to be specific for MaR1) was reported as associated with altered SPM generation in neutrophils (34). The most impacted lipid was claimed to be MaR2. However, the raw data on BioStudies do not evidence any detectable MaR2 in neutrophils (Figure 4 in (37)). Another study claims to detect many diverse SPMs in peritoneal lavage post vagal nerve stimulation. However, on checking raw data for the first SPM, RvD1, in Table 1 in (32), no visible peaks are seen despite detectable levels being reported for the lipid (Figure 4 in (37)). For these two papers, the full set of sample chromatograms for these two lipids are shown as screenshots in [Figures 2,3](#). In summary, data posted online either as part of journal corrections, or in recent published studies from Dalli and colleagues, do not evidence the presence of SPMs.

(ii) Recommendations for oxylipin analysis, and their application to SPM studies.

In 2024, the International Lipidomics Society established an interest group (Oxylipin Analysis IG), as a community-led effort to formulate and publish a set of recommendations on LC-MS/MS analysis of oxylipins for research applications in addition to the existing minimal reporting checklist (43). The main aim was to support researchers to set up methods and process their raw data in line with community best practice for LC-MS/MS methods, noting that these points would equally apply to analysis of all small molecules using this methodology. In this context, the focus was on quantitation conducted in research settings which cannot fully conform to clinical guidelines for reasons that include limited availability of matrix, and lack of availability of analyte-free matrix for validation. A guideline co-authored by around 100 analysts was published early in 2025 (44). Summarizing this, several key principles were agreed:

- (i) the need to use raw/unsmoothed data to calculate signal:noise ratios (S/N).
- (ii) the various ways in which S/N can be calculated, with recommended values for LOD and LOQ of at least 3:1 and 5:1 respectively, based on the standard approach of H/h (H: height of peak, h: height of noise).
- (iii) that all oxylipins being formally quantified should be included as primary standards in standard curves.
- (iv) that secondary/tertiary MRMs should be used for identification purposes, especially for lower abundance oxylipins.

It was also noted that approaches recommended by clinical guidelines based on variance cannot be applied *only in part* to research assays, as that can lead to significant over-interpretation of S/N or peak quality.

Most of the published studies claiming to detect SPMs in biological samples unfortunately do not conform to these criteria. For example, several apply smoothing prior to S/N calculation (34, 45, 46) and/or lack primary standards for all analytes (47-49). Also, algorithms such as the Relative Noise Concept return higher S/N values than the standard approach (7), so that when a cutoff of ≥ 5 is used, poor quality peaks are included in analysis (34, 45, 46). In 2022, reanalysis of data from Dalli et al. on arthritis patient plasma using the above-mentioned criteria failed to confirm the presence of SPMs (7). Following this, raw data from a second study originally claiming to detect SPMs in human skin blisters (50) were independently re-assessed. The new analysis demonstrated that no SPM signals had been present in the original raw data

(18, 51). Last, a recent reanalysis of a third study by a different independent team also concluded that claims made for the presence of SPMs in plasma of mice with inflammatory arthritis were incorrect, with no detectable signals present (52). In summary, three independent reanalyses of raw data by different groups of scientists now raise serious concerns relating to ongoing studies on SPMs being published in the literature by Dalli et al.

Some recent studies from Serhan, Levy and colleagues have included visible chromatographic peaks as representative data. These include publications showing endogenous D-series resolvins in human lung grafts, or lipoxins/RvE4 in dorsal air pouches in response to exogenous supplementation with high amounts of oxygenated PUFA precursors (epoxy-PUFA) (53, 54). However, while one study shows chromatographic peaks for resolvins, the MS/MS fragmentation spectra (Figure 1) are uninterpretable, and no standards are shown to verify retention time. Another study shows spectra that give good visible matches with lipoxins and RvE4. However, chiral analysis of RvE4 to support assignment of the lipid as the 5*S*,15*S*-diHEPE enantiomer was not performed. Neither study reports the LOD/LOQ criteria employed, making it impossible to confirm that only peaks of sufficient quality were integrated. Last, a recent study claimed to detect 17*R*-RvD2 in human saliva and both M2 macrophages and monocytes. Looking at the data in detail, it is noted that (i) spectra for 17*R*-RvD2 do not visibly match the synthetic standard, in particular the large ions seen in the standard at *m/z* 175 and 215 are hardly visible above many other more prominent ions that are not present in the standard for either saliva or cell samples (Figs 2 and 4 in (55)). These spectra do not establish the identity of the lipid. (ii) RvD2 peaks are also seen in cell extract chromatograms, with peaks of similar height to 17*R*-RvD2, and also several other isomers are present with even higher peaks in this channel (Fig 4 in (55)). This pattern of multiple isomers with complex spectra not aligning with standards is strongly suggestive of autoxidation of lipids rather than their enzymatic origin, as discussed below.

(iii) Potential for interference from SPM isomers formed by autoxidation.

During the last 15 years, many studies reported oxylipin levels in plasma, including in healthy subjects, claiming either detectable levels of SPMs, or alternatively reporting extremely poor peaks that could not be integrated (5, 11, 13, 56-64). Aside from methodological differences outlined above, a second potential explanation for this discrepancy relates to processing and storage oxidation artefacts. Indeed, it was recently reported in two studies that fresh plasma does not contain detectable SPMs, unless incorrectly processed (29, 65). Here, chiral and reverse phase LC-MS/MS demonstrated that the detected SPM isomers, putative RvD5, Mar1 and PDX, originated entirely from poor sample handling (29, 65).

SPMs are formally named based on their fully annotated stereochemical structures, for example, RvD1 represents the 7*S*,8*R*,17*S*-form of tri-HDHA with the double bond configuration *trans,trans,cis,trans* between the hydroxylation sites (one specific trihydroxy DHA isomer). In addition, the SPM name infers an enzymatic route to their origin by lipoxygenases (LOXs), cyclooxygenases (COXs) and cytochrome P450 enzymes (CYPs), as outlined in recent reviews and shown in Table 1 (66-68). However, taking the example of RvD1, with DHA as the substrate, there are at least 8 potential isomers based on *S/R* configuration at hydroxylation sites, and several will co-elute using reverse phase chromatography. This does not account for geometric (*cis/trans*) isomer composition which

increases the number of isomers possible, and in the case of tri-hydroxy SPMs can be strongly influenced by the biosynthetic mechanism (69-71). For example, PD1 and its often more abundant isomer, PDX, differ in the configuration of the double bonds as well as chirality. This means that structural assignments of SPMs made based on reverse phase LC alone, need to be approached with caution. A recommendation in the 2025 guideline was to avoid using stereochemical names (and assignment of geometric isomers) for oxylipins unless chirality had been conclusively determined (44). This is particularly an issue for complex tissues where multiple enzymes/cells are present, and autoxidation is a significant potential source of artefacts. Indeed, where multiple isomers are found, autoxidation should always be considered as a formation route, as recently shown in plasma (29, 65).

Raising concerns of autoxidation being a primary source of SPMs more broadly, many studies report multiple mixed isomers of SPMs in cells and tissues detected simultaneously using reverse phase chromatography. In one, three isomers of PD1 (PD1, 17-epi-PD1 and 10*S*,17*S*-PD1) and multiple isomers of MaR1 and lipoxins were shown in human vagal tissue (72). While biochemical routes were proposed, evidence was not provided. As another example, the same PD isomers were shown in mouse thrombi using reverse phase LC (73). The 17-epi-PD1 is also known as “aspirin-triggered-PD1”. As aspirin was not administered, it is not clear how it was formed enzymatically. Further complicating this, in papers reporting multiple isomers, calculated values often show that one or two epimers of each lipid dominate quantitatively. For example, in a study of murine inflammatory arthritis, 17*R*-RvD3, 7*S*,14*S*-diHDHA and 10*S*,17*S*-diHDHA (PDX) were more abundant than their SPM isomers RvD3, MaR1 and PD1 (74). As 17*R*-RvD3 is proposed to be generated by acetylated COX (75), it is again unclear where it originated from as aspirin was not administered. Overall, complex tissues have been often reported to contain a mixture of many SPMs and their isomers making conclusive assignment of their origin impossible. Notably, the above studies used methods that have now been shown to not adhere to community norms, and also included illustrations in place of raw data, making evaluation of the claims impossible.

To address the biosynthetic origin of SPMs in complex tissues, further confirmation is needed using disease models where one or more of the proposed biosynthetic enzymes are genetically deleted, combined with LC-MS/MS SPM analysis using chiral chromatography. While some early studies used chiral analysis to annotate structurally SPMs derived from purified or recombinant enzyme systems (76, 77), none appear to have applied this to the analysis of complex tissues or cells, meaning that the identity of lipids that co-elute with SPM standards was not clearly established. Generally, a stereochemically defined standard was compared with retention time and MS/MS spectra derived from reverse phase chromatography, and assignment of chirality inferred (78-81). Aiming to address this issue, in 2014, a chiral method demonstrated the presence of multiple epimers of LXA₄ in cell culture supernatants from stimulated granulocytes, and the co-incubations of granulocytes with platelets (82). Several other SPMs from DHA including RvD1, 17-epi-RvD1, RvD2, MaR1 and PDX, and the EPA lipid RvE1 were absent. A second paper using chiral separation showed similarly how reverse phase separation alone leads to false positive reporting of LXA₄ from cultured cells, if used without chiral confirmation (83). These studies raise significant questions as to the identity of lipids claimed to be present in early studies on SPMs, further calling into question their biochemical origin in complex tissues.

One recent study partially addressed this using 12/15-LOX (*Alox15*) knockout mice, which generate reduced amounts of precursor mono-hydroxy SPM substrates on challenge with skin wounding, including 17-HDHA (84). Only one SPM was putatively detected in wild type wounds, RvD5. This was previously proposed to originate either from secondary oxygenation of 17S-HDHA by 5-LOX (*Alox5*) at C7, or alternatively through oxygenation of DHA at C7 by 5-LOX, followed by 12/15-LOX oxidation at C17, forming 7S,17S-diHDHA (27, 85). RvD5 is a diHDHA, meaning that exclusive non-enzymatic formation would result in four isomers which all co-elute in RP-chromatography (29), although two diastereomers theoretically could be separated. Chiral analysis in wound tissues suggested several RvD5 isomers were present, like that seen in improperly stored human plasma (29).

(iv) The use of ELISAs as an alternative method for SPM quantification.

Aside from LC-MS/MS, another way to quantify oxylipins including SPMs are enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISA). Although these have been around for decades for PG and other oxylipins, these assays have long been recognized to have significant qualitative and quantitative problems. A recent study shows how ELISAs for SPMs, in particular, RvD1 and RvD2, can detect signals in plasma or serum samples, which according to LC-MS/MS contain no detectable levels of the lipids (86). Furthermore, incorrect processing of plasma by incubation at 37 °C for extended periods, increased the ELISA signals, despite no RvD1 and RvD2 being detected using LC-MS/MS. Manufacturers recommend that data obtained using these kits should be used as a guide and always needs to be verified using LC-MS/MS. However this is not generally being done with many SPM studies being published using ELISA detection alone (60, 87-96). In light of the above-mentioned aspects, claims made using this method (ELISA) without verification by LC-MS/MS need re-evaluation.

(v) Commercial assays for SPMs using LC/MS/MS.

Aside from research laboratories, commercial services for SPM analysis using LC-MS/MS exist. Solutex, offers an LC-MS/MS service as described in several publications (97-99) with LOD based on S/N of >5:1 based on spiking in blanks, without mention of assessing SPM signals in matrix. It also describes matching 6 diagnostic ions in product ion spectra, like methods that do not adhere to community norms. Ambiotis runs an analytical LC-MS/MS service that includes SPMs (100). Recent papers citing their method do not include LOD/LOQ criteria. Furthermore, papers using these methods show no chromatograms to evidence the presence of SPMs in samples (101-103). Last, Cayman provides a commercial assay that adheres to community-agreed approaches (44), but so far this has not reported detection of SPMs in any publications.

(vi) Summary on SPM analytics

In summary, many studies on SPMs have applied LC-MS/MS methods that do not conform to expected standards. Combined with this, ELISAs continue to be used without LC-MS/MS verification, and *ex vivo* autoxidation has recently emerged as a potential significant source of the lipids and their isomers. These issues question many claims about the presence of endogenous SPMs, irrespective of whether their formation is in quantities sufficient to drive the resolution of inflammation.

Enzymatic synthesis of SPMs in cells and tissues

The majority of SPMs are di- or trihydroxylated PUFA derivatives generated through the sequential activity of LOX enzymes, particularly 5-LOX (*ALOX5*) or 15-LOX (*ALOX15*), followed by a second activity, usually another LOX enzyme generating either a dihydro(pero)xide or an LTA₄-related allylic epoxide that hydrolyzes to SPMs. In the case of the LTB₄-related oxylipins MaR1 and PD1, the allylic epoxide is converted to a LTB₄-related structure by a putative hydrolase that has not been identified. Participating LOX include human or murine platelet 12-LOX (*ALOX12*, *Alox12*), human 15-LOX1 (*ALOX15*), human 15-LOX2 (*ALOX15B*), or murine 12/15-LOX (*Alox15*). SPMs are also proposed to be formed by a 12- or 15-LOX acting independently (Figure 1). Generally, monohydroxylated LOX-derived oxylipins are regarded as SPM precursors rather than SPMs themselves. Although LOXs produce abundant mono-hydroxy oxylipins from PUFAs, their capacity to biosynthesize most SPMs appears to be very limited. As discussed in greater detail below, SPM formation is reliably detected only with purified enzymes supplemented with substrates, following addition of high amounts of mono-hydroxy precursors to cells expressing LOX isoforms for secondary oxidation, or through addition of excess PUFAs such as AA or DHA to cells (85, 104-113). Given the expression patterns of these LOX enzymes, SPM biosynthesis is largely confined to leukocytes and is frequently suggested to depend on transcellular transfer of a monohydroxy intermediate from one cell type, such as neutrophils, epithelial cells, or platelets, to another, such as macrophages or neutrophils (109, 114-116). Here, we consider the cellular and enzymatic generation of individual SPM families. Data are summarized from studies considered to have used reliable methods, and/or have shown clearly discernable chromatographic peaks, and that have been replicated by more than one laboratory, unless otherwise stated.

(i) Maresins.

Maresin 1 (MaR1) and MaR2 were proposed as DHA derivatives of a 12-LOX (*ALOX12*) pathway in macrophages, with conversion of 14-HPDHA to a 13*S*,14*S*-epoxide intermediate and its further transformation to maresins by putative epoxide hydrolases (Figure 1) (113). Later it was shown, using recombinant human enzymes, that 15-LOX1 (*ALOX15*) could be involved (Figure 1) (105). MaR1 has an LTB₄-related structure (7*R*,14*S*-dihydroxy with an 8-*trans*,10-*trans*,12-*cis* conjugated triene), but it is not a product of LTA₄ hydrolase that forms LTB₄ (117). MaR2 is a 13*R*,14*S*-diHDHA that can be prepared by reaction of synthetic LTA₄-type 13,14-epoxide with soluble epoxide hydrolase (113). However, evidence that maresins are biosynthesized from endogenous DHA in human macrophages in more than trace amounts, if at all, is lacking with significant levels only reported from recombinant enzymes or when intermediate precursors were added to leukocytes (105, 111-113). Cellular formation of maresins is low, even after bacterial stimulation of M2-like human macrophages (25-27) despite formation of large amounts of the MaR precursor 14-H(p)DHA. Notably, 14-H(p)DHA levels are reported to be several orders of magnitude higher than maresin formation (for review see Table 2 in (118)). We note that these studies used LC methods which, as outlined earlier, do not conform to community norms (7). Furthermore, in another publication claiming MaR2 formation, no chromatograms were shown making data evaluation impossible (30). Overall,

reliable studies indicate that there are at most trace levels (low pg amounts per million cells) of MaRs generated in macrophages, even in the presence of large amounts of their fatty acyl or mono-hydroxy precursors, while studies in tissues used methods where data cannot be verified.

(ii) Protectins.

Analogous to the proposed formation of maresins from 13*S*,14*S*-epoxy-DHA, an 16*S*,17*S*-epoxy-DHA intermediate formed by 15-LOX has been proposed to yield the protectins, PD1 (also named NPD1, Neuroprotectin D1) and PD2 (119). The formation of protectins was proposed from studies where cells or neuronal tissues were supplemented with exogenous DHA or oxylipin precursors (70, 119, 120) or studies where recombinant human 12-LOX, 15-LOX1 or 15-LOX2 was supplied with DHA substrate (106). PD1 was originally prepared and assigned an LTB₄-related structure (a *trans,trans,cis* triene) by biosynthesis using soybean 15-LOX-1 (121). The structure was deduced based on UV and LC-MS analyses both as a product or by-product of soybean LOX activity (albeit going against all precedent and not independently confirmed) (121), and reported as a product of biosynthesis in mammalian cells (122, 123). As noted early on, it is well precedented that soybean LOX will produce a 10*S*,17*S*-diol with 11-*trans*,13-*cis*,15-*trans* conjugated triene and not the *trans,trans,cis* triene assigned to PD1 (69, 124). If isomerization of the well-established soybean LOX product occurred, it would likely give an all-*trans* conjugated triene, but formation of the PD1 structure, a 10*R*,17*S*-diol with *trans,trans,cis* bonds, have never been demonstrated or independently established. PD1 was prepared by total chemical synthesis by four independent groups and the compound is available commercially (125-128). Over the past decade, the existence of PD1 as a cellular product has been challenged based on its similarity to other 10,17-dihydroxy docosanoids (29, 124, 129, 130). The LTB₄-related structure would not be expected as a significant product, based on known mechanisms of polyunsaturated autoxidation (131), as recently confirmed (132), and thorough LC-MS/MS analyses established that PD1 is not among the DHA-related isomers formed in non-enzymatic transformations (29). PD1 can be distinguished from related dihydroxy isomers based on a careful comparison of UV spectra (129), differences in the ratios of product ions by monitoring different transitions (44, 130), and separated from others by normal-phase HPLC (129), although the latter was not applied in the original misidentification of the product from soybean LOX-1 activity (121). Other investigations of 12/15-LOX metabolism of DHA in murine peritoneal macrophages failed to detect PD1 (129). In sum, PD1 has not been demonstrated to form enzymatically, and there is no compelling evidence for its *in vivo* formation.

Another protectin, PDX, with altered double bond geometry is formed by double lipoxygenation of DHA at C10 and C17 (71). Furthermore, only very low amounts of PDs have been observed in M2-like macrophages (25-27) although as stated earlier, these three studies used methods that do not follow community norms. Importantly, the precursor 17-H(p)DHA was detected, exceeding reported PD levels by several orders of magnitude (for review see Table 2 in (118)).

(iii) Lipoxins and resolvins

The biosynthesis of lipoxins from AA or EPA, or D and E series resolvins from EPA and DHA, has been proposed to involve two consecutive oxygenase reactions catalyzed by 5-LOX either

before or after oxygenation by a 12- or 15-LOX isoform (e.g. 12-LOX, 12/15-LOX, 15-LOX1 or 15-LOX2) (Figure 1) (1, 2, 66). The sequence of oxygenation, specifically whether 5-LOX oxygenates first or second depends on the cell types and experimental conditions (for further reading see (6)). Both are considered in more detail below:

(a) The 5-LOX:12/15-LOX pathway

Here, oxygenation is proposed to be first mediated by 5-LOX with the initial products from AA, EPA or DHA being 5*S*-HpETE, 5*S*-HpEPE or 7*S*-HpDHA, respectively. These oxylipins can then serve as substrates for 12- or 15-LOX resulting in a series of dihydroxylated products that notably include 5*S*,15*S*-diHETE and 7*S*,17*S*-diHDHA (RvD5), both consistently detected in human M2 macrophages (118, 133, 134) (Figure 1). Studies with purified enzymes suggest that 15-LOX2 might be involved in RvD5 formation (107).

In addition to the monohydroxylated oxylipins, 5-LOX produces the unstable allylic epoxide LTA₄ from AA (135). This has been proposed to be required for the formation of trihydroxylated SPMs such as lipoxins, since it can serve as substrate for secondary oxygenation by a 12-LOX or 15-LOX isoform (e.g. 12-LOX, 12/15-LOX, 15-LOX1 or 15-LOX2) in leukocyte/platelet coincubations (114, 115, 136). However, epoxide formation by 5-LOX using DHA as substrate has not been demonstrated (137) so that trihydroxylated resolvins of the D series cannot be initially formed via the 5-LOX:12/15-LOX pathway. Due to this, formation of RvD1 and RvD2 requires addition of the epoxide intermediate to neutrophils and macrophages (138). Although prominent lipoxin formation has been observed in neutrophil/platelet coincubations where neutrophil-derived LTA₄ is converted by platelets to lipoxins (114, 115, 136), formation of lipoxins in blood is low or undetectable even after stimulation (139, 140). Here, LTA₄ may be bound to albumin and not available for conversion by platelet 12-LOX (141), which is supported by data showing that addition of recombinant LTA₄ hydrolase in plasma robustly increases the A23187- and fMLF-induced LTB₄ biosynthesis by neutrophils (142). Similarly, LXA₅, 15-*epi*-LXA₅ and RvE4 were recently detected after addition of excess racemic 15-HEPE to human neutrophils (54).

Several publications claim that 5-LOX is involved in the formation of the D-series resolvins RvD3, RvD4, and RvD6 (143, 144). In this context, 5-LOX is hypothesized to first form 4*S*-HDHA from DHA. Following this, the trihydroxylated D-series resolvins RvD3, RvD4, and RvD6 are postulated to form via secondary oxygenation of 4*S*-HDHA by a 12-LOX or 15-LOX isoform. However, no published experimental evidence exists to support this claim. Although 4-*HDHA* formation by 5-LOX has been demonstrated in murine granulocytes (145), human granulocytes only form small amounts of this lipid after DHA supplementation (137), while another study demonstrated that recombinant human 5-LOX is unable to generate 4*S*-HDHA from DHA (107). Notably, 4-*HDHA* and 20-*HDHA* are the two most common autooxidation products of DHA (146, 147). This strongly suggests that 4-*HDHA* may be formed in cell incubations non-enzymatically. In line with this, the formation of 4-*HDHA* is not inhibited by 5-LOX and FLAP inhibitors in stimulated human M1 and M2 macrophages (148), while 4-*HDHA*-derived D-series resolvins are barely detected in human leukocytes (118). Of note, RvD3 and RvD4 were recently demonstrated in human neutrophils, but only when incubated with the synthetic precursor oxylipin 4*S*,5*S*-epoxy-17*S*-HDHA (149). However, considering that a synthetic precursor was added, this study represents nonphysiological conditions and

does not address whether and how these mediators might be formed in leukocytes *in vivo* and if so, which enzymes are involved. In summary, there is no evidence that 5-LOX:12/15-LOX acting in tandem can form endogenous lipoxins and trihydroxylated resolvins *in vivo*.

(b) The 12/15-LOX:5-LOX pathway

The 12/15-LOX:5-LOX pathway is often referred to as a primary route for SPM formation. Here, AA, EPA and DHA are first oxygenated by human 15-LOX1 (ALOX15) or 15-LOX2 (ALOX15B) or CYPs to form the monohydro(pero)xy-fatty acid intermediates: 15-H(p)ETE, 15-H(p)EPE, 18-H(p)EPE or 17-H(p)DHA. Following this, these mediators are further metabolized by 5-LO to form dihydroxylated and trihydroxylated SPMs, such as lipoxins and resolvins. For the formation of trihydroxylated SPMs (Table 1) via this pathway, the generation of an epoxide at carbons 5 and 6 (with AA and EPA derived oxylipins) and at carbons 7 and 8 of 17-H(p)DHA by 5-LOX is proposed to be required. However, current evidence indicates that the monohydro(pero)xylated oxylipins are poor substrates for purified 5-LOX (for review see Table 1 in (118)) and FLAP is also required for their acceptance as substrates in cells (see also below). Of note, formation of dihydroxylated SPMs such as 5*S*,15*S*-diHETE, RvD5 and RvE4 is 1-2 orders of magnitude lower than that of their monohydroxylated precursors, even in stimulated M2-like macrophages which prominently express FLAP, 5-LOX and 15-LOX1 (25, 26, 110, 118, 148, 150-152). In contrast to the monohydroxylated and dihydroxylated oxylipins, formation of trihydroxylated SPMs in leukocytes is extremely low or undetectable by LC-MS/MS. This is likely due to extremely inefficient conversion of oxylipin precursors to the corresponding epoxides by 5-LOX via its LTA₄ synthase activity, which up to now has been shown to require exogenous addition of 15-HETE or 17-HDHA (54, 153) (Figure 1).

The biosynthesis of several E-series resolvins (RvE1, RvE2, RvE3) has been proposed to occur from 18*R*-HEPE (154, 155) (Fig. 1). However, the biosynthetic origin of this oxylipin in human cells is unclear since human LOX isoforms are unable to effectively generate 18*R*-HEPE from EPA (for review see (6)). An alternative source may be CYP enzymes, which can catalyze 18*R*-HETE formation from AA (156), although it is unknown whether analogous reactions occur from EPA. To the best of our knowledge, there is no report showing relevant formation of 18*R*-HEPE from EPA by human CYPs.

(c) FLAP dependency

5-LOX-activating protein (FLAP) has long been known to be required for generation of 5-HETE and LTA₄ from AA by 5-LOX in intact cells (157). Similarly, SPMs such as lipoxins generated via 5-LOX (acting via the 12/15-LOX:5-LOX route), are also considered to be FLAP-dependent (85, 136). Supporting this idea, FLAP is required for 5-LOX-dependent oxygenation of oxylipins including 12- or 15-HETE (158, 159). Alongside this, formation of trihydroxylated SPMs, such as LXA₄ (Table 1) via the 5-LOX:12/15-LOX route is also considered FLAP-dependent. For example, cellular formation of the precursor LTA₄ requires FLAP, while RvD5 biosynthesis via the 12/15-LOX:5-LOX route was recently confirmed to be FLAP-dependent (85). However, contradicting this, RvD5 formation in human M2-like macrophages via the 5-LOX:12/15-LOX pathway was claimed to be FLAP independent in three studies (27, 148, 160). Strikingly, it was also claimed that inhibition of FLAP strongly upregulated SPM biosynthesis. Oddly, in two of these studies, the FLAP inhibitor MK886

reduced formation of the precursor 7-HDHA in M1 cells while simultaneously increasing its formation in M2 cells (27, 148). Several studies have demonstrated that 5-LOX and FLAP are more highly expressed in human M1 cells, so the observation that MK886 prevents 7-HDHA formation in these cells is fully in line with its predicted role in supporting 5-LOX activity (157). How FLAP inhibitors might instead promote activity of 5-LOX to oxidize DHA in one cell type but not another is unclear, also considering that MK886 blocks 7-HDHA formation in human neutrophils (161). FLAP-independent RvD5 formation has only been observed when M2-like cells were stimulated with *Staphylococcus aureus*-conditioned medium but not with calcium ionophore (148) suggesting that this effect is stimulus and cell-type -dependent. Where SPM generation is FLAP independent, it is possible that 5-LOX is not involved and a role for autoxidation driven by macrophage ROS from sources that include NADPH oxidase and myeloperoxidase, can instead be considered (162). This is supported by the observation that the direct 5-LOX inhibitor zileuton was much less effective at blocking formation of 5-HETE generation in human M2-like macrophages than in M1 (148). This suggests significant 5-LOX independent generation of the respective oxylipins in M2 cells under these conditions. Chiral LC-MS/MS analysis would be required to elucidate the stereochemistry of the formed oxylipins to gain more insights into their origin. Furthermore, it is noted that studies proposing FLAP independent SPM formation have all used analytical methods that do not conform to community norms (27, 148, 160). Overall, studies suggesting a role for FLAP in elevating SPM formation in macrophages appear at odds with the proposed role of 5-LOX in this process and need to be re-evaluated.

A second area of discussion relating to the role of FLAP, concerns the idea that cellular location of 5-LOX dictates whether SPMs or leukotrienes are formed in leukocytes, with cytosolic localization favoring SPM formation and translocation to the nuclear membrane fostering pro-inflammatory leukotriene formation (163). This assumption is based on the observation that inhibition of p38 MAPK reduces nuclear localization of 5-LOX and slightly reduces LTB₄ formation whereas LXA₄ formation was increased by 2-fold (163). However, contradicting this idea, the formation of lipoxins is completely FLAP-dependent (85, 136) and FLAP is located in the nuclear membrane (164). This questions the idea that SPM formation is spatially controlled, suggesting that based on current evidence, SPMs (if enzymatically formed) in human leukocytes would occur at the nuclear membrane, like leukotrienes.

(iii) Aspirin-triggered SPMs

Another family of SPMs are termed “aspirin-triggered” (AT-SPMs), since they form through the action of aspirin-acetylated COX-2 (165). Here, monohydroxylated oxylipins with altered stereochemistry are formed which are proposed to then be converted to corresponding AT-SPMs. At present, the relevance of these lipids to the pharmacological actions of aspirin *in vivo* is entirely speculative. No evidence exists for their contribution to either the anti-inflammatory or anti-thrombotic actions of aspirin *in vivo*. Additionally, several studies reported detection of AT-SPMs in tissues where aspirin had not been administered, raising concerns about their artefactual non-enzymatic generation (72-74, 166).

(iv) Summary of evidence on enzymatic and cellular generation of SPMs

The proposed biosynthetic routes for most SPMs require 5-LOX together with either 12/15-LOX (*Alox15*), 15-LOX1 (*ALOX15*), 15-LOX2 (*ALOX15B*), or 12-LOX (*ALOX12*, *Alox12*). Because 5-LOX is expressed almost exclusively in leukocytes, these cells are regarded as central contributors to SPM production. Although both M1-like and M2-like human macrophages express the full enzymatic machinery needed for SPM biosynthesis, their capacity to produce most 5-LOX-dependent dihydroxylated SPMs is limited, whereas trihydroxylated SPMs are barely detectable or not detectable at all. Similar limitations apply to MaRs and PDs. This is thought to reflect intrinsic constraints in LOX-mediated biosynthesis and/or limited mobilization of endogenous fatty acid precursors.

Using methods adhering to current community guidelines (44), the lack of formation of most proposed SPMs in human macrophages and mouse tissues has recently been independently confirmed by Werz et al. (167). Interestingly, the authors interpreted the detection of trace amounts of a small number of dihydroxylated products, including RvD5, RvE4, and PDX, as support for the biological relevance of SPMs and for the hypothesis that these molecules act as endogenous mediators of inflammation resolution. However, the overall dataset supports a different conclusion. Despite the presence of the complete enzymatic machinery required for SPM biosynthesis, the vast majority of proposed SPMs remained undetectable, while those detected were formed only in minute amounts.

Taken together, the available data make it highly unlikely that immune cells generate most proposed SPMs (Table 1) from endogenous fatty acid precursors in amounts sufficient to function as physiologically relevant mediators of inflammation resolution.

Summary and outlook

SPMs have been proposed to function as endogenously produced lipid mediators that coordinate the resolution of inflammation. However, the evidence reviewed here suggests that several core elements of the SPM paradigm require major reassessment, and their role as endogenous drivers of inflammation resolution remains unproven. The original concept is based on quantitative methods with fundamental limitations, possible artefactual generation through *ex vivo* autoxidation, and incorrect assignment as GPCR ligands. Future investigations into SPM biosynthesis and physiology should follow community-recommended analytical standards (44) and apply the strict IUPHAR criteria for receptor identification and validation (168).

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Figure 1 was created in BioRender, Kahnt, A. (2026) <https://BioRender.com/bbnuq10> and <https://BioRender.com/kp6c7p3>.

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NHS, and DS structured the paper, VOD, NHS, MWA, SO and DS wrote and edited the paper. All authors edited the paper.

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Table 1. Mono-, di- and trihydroxylated oxylipins derived from AA, EPA and DHA.

hydroxylation	oxylipin	fatty acid precursor	hydroxylation	involved or proposed human enzymes
monohydroxy derivatives	5 <i>S</i> -HETE ¹	AA	C5	5-LOX
	12 <i>S</i> -HETE	AA	C12	12-LOX, 15-LOX1
	15 <i>S</i> -HETE	AA	C15	15-LOX1, 15-LOX2
	4 <i>S</i> -HDHA ²	DHA	C4	5-LOX
	7 <i>S</i> -HDHA	DHA	C7	5-LOX
	17 <i>S</i> -HDHA	DHA	C17	15-LOX1, 15-LOX2
	5 <i>S</i> -HEPE ³	EPA	C5	5-LOX
	15 <i>S</i> -HEPE	EPA	C15	15-LOX1, 15-LOX2
dihydroxy derivatives	18 <i>R</i> -HEPE	EPA	C18	CYP?
	5,15-diHETE	AA	C5,15	15-LOX ⁴ :5-LOX, 5-LO:15-LO
	8,15-diHETE	AA	C8,15	15-LOX
	resolvin D5 (RvD5)	DHA	C7,17	5-LOX:15-LOX 15-LOX:5-LOX
	resolvin D6 (RvD6)	DHA	C4,17	5-LOX:15-LOX 15-LOX:5-LOX
	maresin 1 (MaR1)	DHA	C7,14	12-LOX, 15-LOX1
	maresin 2 (MaR2)	DHA	C13,14	12-LOX, 15-LOX1
	protectin D1 (PD1)	DHA	C10,17	12-LOX, 15-LOX
	protectin D2 (PD2)	DHA	C16,17	12-LOX, 15-LOX
	protectin DX (PDX)	DHA	C10,17	12-LOX, 15-LOX
	resolvin E2 (RvE2)	EPA	C5,18	CYP?:5-LOX
	resolvin E3 (RvE3)	EPA	C17,18	CYP?
	resolvin E4 (RvE4)	EPA	C5,15	15-LOX:5-LOX, 5-LOX:15-LOX
	trihydroxy derivatives	lipoxin A ₄ (LXA ₄)	AA	C5,6,15
lipoxin B ₄ (LXB ₄)		AA	C5,14,15	5-LOX:12- or 15-LOX
resolvin D1 (RvD1)		DHA	C7,8,17	15-LOX:5-LOX
resolvin D2 (RvD2)		DHA	C7,16,17	15-LOX:5-LOX
resolvin D3 (RvD3)		DHA	C4,11,17	15-LOX:5-LOX
resolvin D4 (RvD4)		DHA	C4,5,17	15-LOX:5-LOX
resolvin E1 (RvE1)		EPA	C5,12,18	CYP? or (15-LOX):5-LOX

¹hydroxyeicosatetraenoic acid, ²hydroxydocosaheptaenoic acid, ³hydroxyeicosapentaenoic acid

**5-Lipoxygenase :
12-/15-Lipoxygenase
Pathway**

**12-/15-Lipoxygenase :
5-Lipoxygenase
Pathway**

Fig. 1 Proposed biosynthetic pathways for SPMs. The red circles indicate reactions which are not enzymatically supported. The epoxy fatty acid intermediates refer to the LOX-mediated allylic epoxides proposed to be formed from the respective fatty acid hydroperoxide precursor.

MaR2 m/z 359.3 \rightarrow 191.1 MaR2 359.3 \rightarrow 221.1

Fig. 2 Signals of maresin 2 (MaR2) MRM transitions in standard and samples. Data extracted from the raw data provided by Gomez et al. (34). Unsmoothed signals.

Fig. 3 Signals of resolvins D1 (RvD1) MRM transitions in standard and samples. Data extracted from the raw data provided by Caravaca et al. (32). Unsmoothed signals.